

The impact of pedagogical translanguaging in enhancing communicative competence of university students in Lesotho

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This article reports on the impact of translanguaging in enhancing communicative competence of the university students in three selected institutions in Lesotho. Data were collected through focus group interviews with ninety ($N=90$) selected students from the three selected institutions and face-to-face semi-structured interviews with nine ($N=9$) lecturers from the three institutions as well. The findings reveal that most students prefer being taught in both the target language and their mother-tongue instead of only the target language. These findings highlight the importance of adopting pedagogical translanguaging in the classroom so that students from all backgrounds can be included in their own learning. Future research should therefore focus on how pedagogical translanguaging can be adopted in ESL classroom so that students can have a liberty to draw from their mother tongue in cases where they encounter challenges with the target language.

Keywords: Bilingualism; Communicative Competence; English as Second Language (ESL); Pedagogical Strategy; Translanguaging

1. Introduction

In Lesotho and elsewhere in the world, second language learning and acquisition has seen a major shift in pedagogical paradigm. This is because the use of mother tongue (L1) in an English language classroom—which Salmani Nodoushan (2023) has referred to as a ‘petri dish’ or a ‘panopticon’—was perceived to be an impediment rather than a good teaching approach (Abrahamson, 2009; Chambers, 1991; Ellis, 1984; Tabatabaei, 2019; Yuzlu & Dikilitas, 2022). However, many researchers have since advocated for translanguaging as an alternative pedagogical strategy (cf. Chaka, 2024; Motaung, (2024); Xu & Fang; 2024);¹ it brings about lively learning atmosphere in which students in the context of this study can use their stronger L1 (Sesotho) and a weaker L2 (English) freely in the classroom (Childs, 2016; Elashhab, 2020; Makalela, 2015, 2020; Yuzlu & Dikilitas, 2022). Research

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argues that translanguaging should be used as an alternative pedagogical strategy because it permits the use of both languages in the classroom which in turn benefits students (Cenoz & Gorter, 2020; Garcia, 2009). In consonance, Elashhab (2020) and Sefotho (2022) substantiate that translanguaging is an attractive pedagogical strategy that should be adopted because of its positive impact on language learning and also promotes diversity and plurality in the classroom. The above-mentioned postulations imply that translanguaging has the affordance, à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021a), to be a very good teaching strategy in an English language classroom (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016).

Research has been conducted on the impact that pedagogical translanguaging has on the enhancement of students' communicative competence (cf. Canale & Swain, 1980; Tumansery & Munden, 2020) in the English language. For instance, Yuzlu and Dikilitas (2022) found that translanguaging improves students' communicative abilities, their receptive and productive skills as well as an improved communication between students and lecturers. Furthermore, Aung (2021), Elashhab (2020), Makalela (2015), and Sefotho (2022) found that translanguaging improves classroom participation, expedites meaningful content learning and stimulates vocabulary learning as well. Riswanto (2022) also found that students can easily understand what the lecturer is presenting, and they also become active in responding to questions asked by teachers. The aforementioned findings stipulate that translanguaging can be a very good pedagogical strategy in an ESL classroom. However, there are no studies conducted in Lesotho on the impact that pedagogical translanguaging has on students' communicative competence. This study therefore sought to fill this gap by finding out the impact of pedagogical translanguaging on the enhancement of university students' communicative competence in the three selected institutions in Lesotho. The study therefore sought to answer the following research questions:

1. How do students react to translanguaging in an ESL classroom?
2. How do lecturers employ pedagogical translanguaging in their classrooms?

The study adopted Vygotsky's socio-cultural theory of second language learning and acquisition. This theory views language learning and acquisition as the product of interaction between lecturers and students. The theory stresses interaction as another means of developing students' communicative competence skills in the classroom. Interaction stimulates comprehensible output which might come out as the input delivered by lecturers to students (Shannon, 2011). Students would in turn express evocative or comprehensible utterances (output) because of being in control of their learning, while lecturers act as facilitators, or scaffolders (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016), who

chiefly help them (students) where they come upon communication breakdown during the negotiation of meaning amongst themselves. The researcher's view is therefore that allowing students to use their mother tongue during negotiation of meaning can avert communication breakdowns because students can use their L1 to compensate that gap in communication. The conception of scaffolding thus becomes central in second language learning and acquisition (Engeström, 1999; see also Salmani Nodoushan, 2016).

Scaffolding is accordingly defined in terms of the help which is given to the student so that their intellectual potential is met (Hamachek, 1995; Turuk, 2008). The researcher believes that this help can be in the form of allowing students to convey their ideas or answers in their mother tongue in cases where they find it difficult to express their feelings in the target language. Furthermore, Donato (2000) describes scaffolding as a condition which is constructed by a teacher, peer or parent in which the student can partake and augment their present abilities and knowledge to higher levels of performance. The assumption in the context of this study is that students can reach those higher levels of performance if they are allowed to use their mother tongue in cases where they encounter challenges in the target language. This further suggests that lecturers can help students by teaching them in their L1 so that they can understand better.

Vertical scaffolding entails the role played by parents or mentors by asking students more questions under any topic studied in class while sequential scaffolding takes place when students partake in games which are aimed at improving their vocabulary and speaking skills. Lastly, instructional scaffolding is believed to be at the centre of teaching or in tutorials where a lecturer assists students in designing the learning chore. It was important therefore to find out the type of scaffolding offered in the development of students' communicative competence skills especially the use of translanguaging strategy in the classroom.

There are four subgroups of scaffolding in the process of instructional scaffolding: (a) conceptual, (b) metacognitive, (c) procedural, and (d) strategic scaffolding (Hannafin et al., 2014). In conceptual scaffolding, lecturers drill their students to concentrate on the extent of the description of the problem which might be found within the task. On the contrary, metacognitive scaffolding supports students in organising their thinking, suggesting possible resolutions when working on a problem as well as thinking upon the continuous course of action during the analysis of, and solution to, the task. Students who have developed this kind of strategy tend to do better than those who have not (Hannafin et al., 2014). The researchers therefore believe that students who are exposed to translanguaging have an advantage in this regard

because their receptive and productive skills are enhanced as found by (Cummins, 1978; 2000; Klaus, 2003; Stoop, 2017; Thomas & Collier 1997). Moreover, procedural scaffolding offers advice and backing to students on the basis of their understanding of the uses and functions of language. Lastly, strategic scaffolding instructs the students on wide-ranging strategies when analysing problems as well as approaching such a problem. For instance, students can apply this strategy when trying to find an alternative answer to answering quickly the cognitive gap in a verbal task (Bannert, 2002; de Jong, 2010). The researchers were further interested in finding out how lecturers help students with low cultural capital to develop their metacognitive strategies which lead to good performance (Hannafin et al., 2014).

2. Background

Translanguaging is the capacity or ability to use two or more languages in a single lesson in the classroom (Baker, 2001; Baker, 2011; Canagarajah, 2011; İlhan & Özkan, 2021; Otherguy et al., 2015; Williams, 1994). MacSwan (2017) posits that different authors such as Bakhtin (1981), Canagarajah (2011), Canagarajah (2013), Jørgensen (2008), Jørgensen et al. (2011), and Otsuji and Pennycook (2011) have proposed terms or concepts that are similar and employed slightly differently from translanguaging, and they comprise heteroglossia, metrolingualism, code-meshing, polylinguaging and polylingual languaging, translingual practice, and multilinguaging. Therefore, a multilingual standpoint on translanguaging recognises the existence of a distinct language and multilingualism, and it also embraces students' right to be taught in their mother tongue as well as the second language (Canales, 2022; Celic & Seltzer, 2011; İlhan & Özkan, 2021; Macswan, 2017; Prilutskaya, 2021; Zhou et al., 2020). This process of teaching students in both Sesotho and English in the context of this study suggests that social justice can be achieved; that is, both languages are equal and students are free to resort to their mother tongue any time they encounter challenges.

There is a backing from literature that advocates the use of mother tongue in language education, and education in general, as a move that will undo the past and current wrongs that ostracised and discriminated against the use of L1 (Garcia & Li, 2014; Hurst & Mona, 2017; Makalela, 2015; Mgiijima & Makalela, 2016; Yuzlu & Dikilitas, 2022; Zhou et al., 2020). Baker (2011) is of the view that translanguaging enhances students' academic language competencies in both languages (L1 and L2). There are authors who believe that students who began school in their L1 tend to perform better than most of their counterparts who started with L2 (Cummins, 1978; 2000; Klaus, 2003; Stoop, 2017; Thomas & Collier 1997). Furthermore, Estyn (2002) and Yuzlu and Dikilitas (2022) substantiate that translanguaging helps students to alternate between

languages in written and spoken as well as receptive and productive modes which enhance their understanding of concepts.

Moreover, translanguaging permits students to figure out and take full advantage of their capabilities in the learning of one language by means of the skills of the already existing lexicon (Nyimbili & Mwanza, 2021; Włosowicz, 2020). In addition, Garcia (2009) agrees that in translanguaging, languages are no longer allocated separate fields or purposes, but they exist together in the same space as well as not being evaluated in terms of their prominence in society. Therefore, pedagogical translanguaging is an essential instructive strategy in today's didactic practices (Afitska, 2020; Makalela, 2015; Obi et al., 2021). Likewise, Baker (2001) outlines four educational advantages of pedagogical translanguaging as follows:

1. Translanguaging can encourage a deeper and complete comprehension of the subject matter.
2. It may possibly assist the gradual growth of the weaker language.
3. Translanguaging can make possible home-school links and collaboration.
4. It may also facilitate the assimilation of communicatively competent speakers with beginners.

However, authors such Akbar and Taqi (2020) and Taqi and Shuqair (2014) argue that translanguaging does not improve students' linguistic capabilities. In consonance, Krause and Prinsloo (2016) found that translanguaging did not improve learners' grammatical competence because most of them committed spelling mistakes and displayed poor command of English. Furthermore, Nyimbili and Mwanza (2021) and Park (2013) assert that translanguaging lacks substantial sets of teaching methodologies to smooth the progress of language learning and academic achievement. Another finding from Escobar and Paltrineri (2015) reveals that students are against the notion of translanguaging because they believe that "L1 use in the classroom too closely resembles translation and would detract from the methods of communicative language teaching" (Escobar & Paltrineri, 2015, p. 312). This finding implies that students feel that translanguaging does not enhance their communicative competence in the target language. Given the above findings, the study therefore sought to find out if translanguaging enhanced students' communicative competence skills in the Lesotho university context.

The researchers' synthesis given the above postulations on translanguaging is that it can be a good strategy if students are expected to understand the concepts in class; however, the researchers do not think that it can improve

students' communicative competence skills; especially those from rural schools who already have poor command of the English language. But then again, the researchers want to believe that there are students as well as lecturers who might see it otherwise because the teaching and learning of English can never be perceived in the same manner. It is therefore important to find out what the findings of the study reveal regarding this matter.

3. Method

In this study, a qualitative research approach was adopted. The rationale for the approach is that the researchers view the nature of reality through interpretivist lenses when attempting to comprehend human experiences (Chilisa, 2011; Jalongo & Saracho, 2016). This approach suggests that the researchers attempt to understand both lecturers' and students' experiences concerning the impact of pedagogical translanguaging in enhancing students' communicative competence in the English language.

Aspers and Corte (2021) Cropley (2015), Denzin and Lincoln (2005), Jameel et al. (2018), and Mohajan (2018) see a qualitative research approach as normally based on a situated activity which studies things in their natural setting and makes sense of the phenomena in terms of the meanings people assign to them—for more on meaning, see Salmani Nodoushan (2022). Hence, Creswell (2014) describes qualitative research as an approach that is used to investigate an individual's interpretations and responses to social problems.

Furthermore, the study adopted a case study design—See also Salmani Nodoushan, (2023). Merriam (1998) and Yin (2018) defines a case study as an experiential method that examines a current phenomenon or the case in profoundness and inside its context in the real-world, particularly when the limitations between a phenomenon and the context might not be visibly apparent. In this study, the researchers' focus was mainly on investigating (a) individual and (b) collective teaching and learning and (c) the impact of translanguaging on the enhancement of students' communicative competence and performance in English as a second language.

At times, attention was paid to a single case possibly because of its distinctive or exceptional qualities which could promote a certain understanding or inform practice for similar situations (Creswell, 2003; Leedy & Ormrod, 2016). A case study was therefore appropriate in learning further about a little known or a situation that is not well understood (Burns, 2010). A case study was therefore befitting in this context because the study aimed at exploring a little-known phenomenon brought about by lack of research in Lesotho into the phenomenon among the tertiary ESL students in regard to the impact of pedagogical translanguaging in the development of their communicative competence skills.

3.1. Participants

The sample of the study was purposively selected from three institutions, and it consisted lecturers and students from the selected institutions. Bryman (2008) refers to sample as the division or representative of the population under investigation. Samples for qualitative studies are usually smaller (Leedy & Ormrod, 2016). As a result, findings from those studies are not broadly generalisable. This implies that the findings of this study were not generalised to other institutions, but they were generalised to the sampled institutions. For anonymity purposes, both lecturers and students were assigned labels during discussions and interviews. Male students were given Sm, while females were assigned Sf. Male lecturers were assigned Lm, while female lecturers were given Lf labels.

3.2. Materials

Focus group discussions with students ($N=90$) and face-to-face interviews lecturers ($N=9$) were employed as the data collection tools in this study. A focus group discussion entails gathering people from analogous backgrounds or skills together in order to deliberate a particular topic of interest (Nyumba et al., 2018). It is a type of qualitative research in which participants are asked questions about their insights, attitudes, beliefs, and opinions (Nyumba et al., 2018). In a focus group discussion, participants are at liberty to talk to other group members. It usually consists of 8 to 12 participants led by an interviewer (researcher) in a flexible discussion of various topics of interest (Krueger & Casey, 2000). Furthermore, the study employed face-to-face interviews with lecturers. An interview involves asking questions and getting answers from the selected population (Creswell, 2014). This can be telephonic, face-to-face, in the form of a focus-group discussion, structured, semi-structured, or unstructured (Creswell, 2012). Therefore, data in this study were collected through face-to-face interviews which were largely conversational with nine ($N=9$) lecturers from the three selected institutions.

3.3. Procedure

For conducting this study, it was vitally important to obtain permission from the relevant authorities. Obtaining such permission would, in turn, allow the researcher to avoid going to other people's workplaces without consent (Creswell, 2012). The second researcher conducting the procedures thus introduced himself to the participants with an ethical clearance certificate number (i.e., 10260307_CRECHS_2021) from the University of South Africa (UNISA). Furthermore, this researcher applied both morality and fairness criteria to his ethical conduct as stipulated by Kivunja and Kuyini (2017). The morality criterion denotes the fundamental moral values that the researcher

maintained during the research while fairness refers to the researcher's ability to be impartial to all research participants in the course of data collection thus ensuring that their rights are sustained (Akaranga & Makau, 2016; Kivunja & Kuyini, 2017). As such, the researcher treated the participants equally, and then interpreted the data as objectively as possible by reflecting on the participants' views when drawing his conclusions from the study.

Moreover, the data in this study were analysed thematically through inductive thematic analysis procedure as stipulated by Braun and Clarke (2006), Frith and Gleeson (2004), and Hayes (2000). First of all, the data were organised into categories, thereby identifying codes pertinent to the topic of the study. Furthermore, smaller lumps of meaning which bore similar properties were further grouped and then assigned transitory descriptions or themes. This procedure paved the way for analogous chunks of text to be included into different data sets. Lastly, the data were then systematically modified to make sure that a name, a description, and a comprehensive data set to back each group or category were recognised (Frith & Gleeson, 2004). To ensure the credibility of the findings, the study was taken back to the participants; mainly lecturers in order to check if their views were properly reflected as well as discussing the implications of the findings to their teaching approaches. Additionally, the study was scrutinised by the supervisor to ensure that it was well carried out and then provided comments. The study was further taken to peers who were experts in the field of language teaching for their constructive criticism, and thereafter, it was sent to the editor who ensured that it was properly written and well presented.

4. Results

4.1. Focus group discussions

The following three themes were revealed by findings from the focus group discussions with students ($N=90$): (a) understanding, (b) participation, and (c) confidence.

Many students revealed that translanguaging helped them to 'understand' some concepts that are not easy in English. They reported that they do not easily forget such concepts when they are explained in Sesotho. One student (Sm1) said the following:

I am not fluent in English because I am from a public school where we hardly spoke English, so it is not easy to keep up with the tertiary English. I am one of those students who keep asking lecturers to explain some of the things in Sesotho because I understand better when they also use Sesotho.

Other students also revealed that translanguaging was a good strategy for them because it allows them to translate from Sesotho to English and from English to Sesotho. Therefore, thinking in their own language is very important because they cannot easily forget what was taught in their mother tongue.

In terms of 'participation', students reported that translanguaging increased their eagerness to partake in classroom activities. They revealed that participation comes as a result of understanding. This means that they are able to participate because they understand what is being taught, and they would not participate if they did not understand what was being said to them. One student (Sf20) expressed the following:

It is easy to take part in what you understand, so lecturers who explain things in both English and Sesotho makes it easy for us to feel the need to partake in our learning.

Students further revealed that translanguaging increased their 'confidence'. They reported that they sometimes answer some questions in Sesotho if they know the answer but having difficulties to express themselves in English. This implies that even those students who have a poor command of English will feel included. One student (Sm40) expressed themselves as follows:

Being able to use my language in the classroom gives me confidence to speak and to take part in classroom activities. I am not shy of making mistakes unlike when things are only done in English.

Students' revelations regarding the use of translanguaging in an EFL/ESL class, or 'petri dish' à la Salmani Nodoushan (2023), imply that it is a good strategy because it increases their understanding, confidence, and participation in the classroom. They further suggest that translanguaging creates a positive ambiance in which all students regardless of their English backgrounds take part in their own learning. However, it is not clear if translanguaging improves students' communicative competence skills besides increasing confidence, understanding, and participation.

4.2. Lecturer interviews

Interviews with lecturers sought to find their responses to the following two questions:

1. When do you employ translanguaging in your classroom?
2. How do students react to translanguaging in an ESL classroom?

As for the first question, many local lecturers whose L1 was Sesotho revealed that they were expected to teach in English since it was regarded as the medium of instruction, but they sometimes or mostly explain some concepts in Sesotho. Even those who did not speak Sesotho mentioned that they allowed their students to speak in Sesotho in cases where they got stuck, but they would thereafter ask other students to translate for them and other students who might not understand English.

I teach bilingual students, so it is of utmost importance that I use both languages in class because I have realised that they understand better when you explain most of the concepts in Sesotho. It also enhances their translation skills because they can think in their own language and then translate their answers to English. (Lm11)

Another observation was made by another lecturer (Lm10), and he expressed the following views:

If you come to class and start speaking English throughout, you'd see students who are not happy at all given the background of most of them. By the time you ask them questions, they will ask you to repeat what you were saying in Sesotho because they would genuinely have not understood. So, using both English and Sesotho encourage my students to participate fully.

Similar observation was made by (Lm5) regarding students' expectations in the use of translanguaging.

I may not understand Sesotho but in order to accommodate everyone when someone is stuck, I would say how do you say that in Sesotho and then ask the class to translate so that everyone participate[s] because at times you are discussing issues and then people become emotional and expressing themselves in English is impossible. Once they become emotional, I will say it's okay express yourself in Sesotho and then I throw it back to class. In this way my students tend to feel free when their language is used.

The above comments seem to imply that students are not comfortable with the direct method, but they become at ease once lecturers employ translanguaging.

Lecturers further added that they use both English and Sesotho in their classrooms because their aim was to decolonise the curriculum. Their aim is therefore to change students' mindset by knowing that their L1 is equally important, so they do not have to feel ashamed of their language. Even though they want their students to be communicatively competent in English given its

global status, they further highlighted that it was also imperative to include students' native languages so that they could appreciate both languages.

As to the second question, many lecturers reported that most of their students felt comfortable when they (i.e., the lecturers) used both Sesotho and English to teach. They further revealed that using both languages increased participation especially amongst students who do not have a proper English background. One lecturer (Lm5) expressed the following:

Students tend to participate more because they understand much better when I teach them in both languages. Those who benefit most when I teach in both English and Sesotho are students from rural schools because they are very shy and they hardly speak when I use direct method, but they participate a lot when I use two languages.

Another lecturer added that students from rural schools have poor command of English because of lack of exposure, so they often struggle to cope with the pace at which content is delivered. They therefore have to resort to Sesotho so that those students can understand as well and not be left behind. Another issue that emerged is that some students do not like to be taught in their mother tongue because they feel like their English will suffer as a result. One lecturer (Lf2) said:

I do not like to overdo it because students' English suffer[s] when I use Sesotho, and there are other students who do not like to be taught in Sesotho at all, but I still do it for the sake of those students who struggle to understand when I teach only in English.

It is possible given the above comments that some lecturers have a challenge of trying to satisfy two sets of students; those whose English is poor and others with good command of the language. However, it is also important that all students be given a chance to take part in their learning, especially those who have poor background of English. Nevertheless, it is crucial that students with good command of English because of exposure from early age be helped as well to maintain that competence. For that reason, it is possible that students' reaction is not the same because translanguaging seems to favour students with poor command of English while it does not benefit those with good command of the language. It is likely therefore that translanguaging may not enhance students' communicative competence; rather it increases understanding and participation.

5. Discussion

Findings reveal that translanguaging is one of the strategies that lecturers employ in their classroom. Lecturers reported that they were supposed to

teach students in English since it was the medium of instruction; however, they found it befitting to explain most of the concepts in Sesotho where students did not understand. This finding was corroborated by most of students who agreed that they did not feel comfortable when lecturers only taught in English. They further elaborated that they participated more in classroom activities where they understood better. That is, they understood easily in instances where lecturers taught in both English and Sesotho. This finding is supported by Estyn (2002) and Yuzlu and Dikilitas (2022) who substantiate the claim that translanguaging makes it easier for students to alternate between languages. Additionally, this finding resonates with Baker's (2011) view that translanguaging enhances students' academic language competencies in both languages (i.e., L1 and L2).

Moreover, there is backing from literature that advocates the use of mother tongue in language education, and education in general, as a move that will undo the past and current wrongs that ostracised and discriminated against the use of L1 from authors such as Al Balushi (2020), Garcia and Li (2014), Hurst and Mona (2017), Makalela (2015), Mgijima and Makalela (2016), and Zhou et al. (2020) seem to get support from both lecturers and students in the use of Sesotho and English in the classroom. Furthermore, the use of translanguaging is seen as promoting 'social justice' by empowering minority languages even in environments that advocate monolingual pedagogies (Szelei et al., 2021). This is because both lecturers and students have a better understanding when concepts are explained in both Sesotho and English.

The researchers therefore believe that translanguaging creates a positive environment in which lecturers can scaffold learning as well as allow students to have an experience of learning in their own language (Ayob, 2020; Garcia and Li, 2014; Mgijima & Makalela, 2016). It can also be helpful in other disciplines because it fosters interaction and participation from students. In agreement, Aung (2021) found that students got great marks because of translanguaging. However, Aung also found that students made spelling mistakes especially in English, Afrikaans, and other home languages. Aung's finding is consistent with Krause and Prinsloo's (2016) finding that students made a lot of spelling mistakes during examinations because of translanguaging. Akbar and Taqi (2020) found that translanguaging did not improve students' L2 as earlier claimed by Baker (2011); however, it only showed a difference of 0.3 (6%). Taqi and Shuqair (2014), as cited in Akbar and Taqi (2020), have also revealed that students who were taught by the same lecturers for four years in one department did not show any improvement in their competence in English due to translanguaging. Nevertheless, the researchers are of the view that students will do better if they are taught with their L1 alongside the target language because they understand more easily as depicted in literature when some concepts are explained in their language.

6. Conclusion

Given the lack of research on the impact of pedagogical translanguaging in enhancing students' communicative competence in English in Lesotho, the current study sought to investigate if translanguaging has any impact on students' level of English. This is because findings from different studies such as Baker (2011), Makalela (2020), Obi et al. (2021), Sefotho (2022), Włosowicz (2020), and Yuzlu and Dikilitas (2022) reveal that translanguaging expedites comprehension and learning in the classroom. Findings from this study also reveal that translanguaging increases students' confidence, understanding, and participation. However, the findings do not reveal any impact on enhancing students' communicative competence. Nevertheless, this lack of impact does not render pedagogical translanguaging a bad strategy because of its aforementioned positive effects in the classroom. Furthermore, findings regarding students' reaction to translanguaging in an ESL classroom reveal that many students especially those with poor command of English participate a lot in classroom activities when some concepts are explained in both English and Sesotho. They also get highly motivated when they understand what is being said in class. Finally, findings in regard to the question of how lecturers employ pedagogical translanguaging in their classrooms reveal that they use it when students do not understand the materials or when they explain certain concepts.

The study therefore recommends that pedagogical translanguaging should be a strategy that is adopted at high school level as well as tertiary because it serves as a scaffolding activity (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016) that both teachers and lecturers can use to facilitate learning, and it also promotes social justice by giving minority languages a chance to be used beside the target language in the classroom. It is further recommended that pedagogical translanguaging be used intensively as a strategy in other disciplines where much clarification of concepts is needed and then be used minimally in an English language classroom so that students can be amply exposed to the target language. This is because many students from rural schools complained about lack of language exposure at high school, so teaching them with the language that helps them to understand will make them understand and participate more in the classroom. They will not feel anxious knowing that they are free to express themselves in their language. This will definitely promote diversity in the classroom.

All in all, the main 'washback', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021b), of this study is to draw attention to the role that pedagogical translanguaging plays in students' learning. Even though the study sought to investigate its impact on enhancing students' communicative competence in English, findings revealed that pedagogical translanguaging facilitates learning, increases understanding,

motivates participation as well as enhances students' confidence. It is further believed that pedagogical translanguaging can be a good scaffolding strategy that teachers and lecturers can use in the classroom since it increases students' understanding and confidence. The results of this study cannot be generalisable to other institutions apart from the ones that took part in the study; thus, more research with a different approach from the one employed herein is needed to further investigate if pedagogical translanguaging can be a strategy that can replace the monoglossic approach to language teaching, and how it can help towards the promotion of diversity and plurality of languages in the classroom.

Notes:

1. For more on relevant topics including activism, diversity, decolonisation epistemologies, multilingualism, translanguaging, equity, social justice, and other relevant (socio)educational topics, please see Balosa (2024), Chaka (2024), Hannaford and Alexander (2024), Huang (2024), Kruger-Marias (2024), Mapuya (2024), Motaung (2024), Ndlangamandla (2024), Ndlangamandla et al. (2024), and Xu and Fang (2024).

Authors' Statement

The authors discussed and conceived the article together. In particular, Dr Shange is the supervisor and she made sure that the whole document was written properly. She made comments and then proof-read the manuscript. Nkhi is the supervisee, and he wrote the whole document under the supervision of Dr Shange. This manuscript is part of the thesis submitted in accordance with the requirement for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy at the University of South Africa.

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References

- Abrahamson, N. (2009). *Second language learning*. Studentlitteratur.
- Afitska, O. (2020). Translanguaging in diverse multilingual classroom in England: Oasis or a mirage? *The European Journal of Applied Linguistics and TEFL* 9(1), 153-181.
- Akaranga, S. I., & Makau, B. K. (2016). Ethical considerations and their applications to research: A Case of the University of Nairobi. *Journal of Educational Policy and Entrepreneurial Research*, 3(12), 1-9.
- Akbar, R. S. S., & Taqi, H. A. (2020). Translanguaging as an ESL learning strategy: A case study in Kuwait. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 9(6), 54-63. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v9n6p54>
- Al Balushi, H. M. A. R. (2020). The reasons of using L1 in the ESL classroom. *Language Teaching Research Quarterly* 16, 56-70. <https://doi.org/10.32038/ltreq.2020.16.04>.
- Aspers, P., & Corte, U. (2021). What is qualitative in research? *Qualitative Sociology*, 44, 599-608. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11133-021-09497-w>
- Aung, S. (2021). *Perceptions of translanguaging amongst English teachers in township primary schools* [Unpublished Master's Thesis]. University of Pretoria.
- Ayob, S. (2020). *The utilisation of translanguaging for learning and teaching in multilingual primary classrooms* [Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation]. University of Pretoria.
- Baker, C. (2001). *Foundations of bilingual education and bilingualism* (3rd ed.). Multilingual Matters.
- Bakhtin, M. (1981). *The dialogic imagination: Four essays*. University of Texas Press.

- Balosa, D. (2024). Existential sociolinguistics and existential justice: Addressing minority-language issues in multilingual societies. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2). [in press]
- Bannert, M. (2002). Managing cognitive load—Recent trends in cognitive load theory. *Learning and Instruction*, 12(1), 139-146. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-4752\(01\)00021-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-4752(01)00021-4)
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3, 77-101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Bryman, A. (2008). *Social research methods* (3rd ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Burns, A. (2010). Doing action research in English language teaching: A guide for practitioners. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203863466>
- Canagarajah, S. (2011). Code meshing in academic writing: Identifying teachable strategies of translanguaging. *The Modern Language Journal* 95(3), 401-417. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.2011.01207.x>
- Canagarajah, S. (2013). *Translanguaging practice: Global English and cosmopolitan relations*. Routledge.
- Canale, M., & Swain, M. (1980). Theoretical bases of communicative approaches to second language teaching and testing. *Applied Linguistics*, 1(1), 1-47.
- Canals, L. (2022). The role of the language of interaction and translanguaging on attention to interactional feedback in virtual exchanges. *System*, 105, 2-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2022.102721>
- Celic, C., & Seltzer, K. (2011). Translanguaging: A CUNY-NYSIEB guide for educators. *CUNY-NYS Initiative on Emergent Bilinguals*, 1-184.
- Cenoz, J., & Gorter, D. (2020). Teaching English through pedagogical translanguaging. *World Englishes*, 39, 300-311. <https://doi.org/10.1111/weng.12462>
- Chaka, C. (2024). Multilingualism, translanguaging, diversity, equity, social justice, and activism: A tenuous nexus and misrepresentations? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 7-28.

- Chambers, F. (1991). Promoting use of the target language in the classroom. *Language Learning Journal*, 4, 27-31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09571739185200411>
- Childs, M. (2016). Reflecting on translanguaging in multilingual classrooms: Harnessing the power of poetry and photography. *Educational Research for Social Change*, 5(1), 22-40. <https://dx.doi.org/10.17159/2221-4070/2016/v5i1a2>
- Chilisa, B. (2011). *Indigenous research methodologies*. Sage. sagepub.com/en-us/nam/indigenous-research-methodologies/book241776
- Creswell, J. W. (2003). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approached* (2nd ed.). Sage.
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Planning, conducting and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). Pearson Education International.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Cropley, A. (2015). *Creativity in education and learning: A guide for teachers and educators*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203826270>
- Cummins, J. (1978). Bilingualism and development of metalinguistic awareness. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 9(2), 131-149. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002202217892001>
- Cummins, J. (2000). *Language, power and pedagogy: Bilingual children in the crossfire*. Multilingual Matters. <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781853596773>
- De Jong, T. (2010). Cognitive load theory, educational research, and instructional design: Some food for thought. *Instructional Science*, 38, 105-134. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11251-009-9110-0>
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2005). Introduction: The discipline and practice of qualitative research. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *The Sage handbook of qualitative research* (pp 1-32). Sage.
- Donato, R. (2000). Sociocultural contributions to understanding the foreign and second language classroom. In J. P. Lantolf (Ed.), *Sociocultural theory and second language learning* (pp. 27-52). Oxford University Press.

- Elashhab, S. (2020). The impact of translanguaging on the EFL competence development of Arabic speaking learners. *Asian EFL Journal*, 27(3), 393-413.
- Ellis, R. (1984). *Classroom second language development*. Pergamon.
- Engeström, Y. (1999). Activity theory and individual and social transformation. In Y. Engeström, R. Miettinen & R.-L. Punamäki (Eds.), *Perspectives on activity theory* (pp. 19-38). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511812774.003>
- Escobar, C. F., & Paltrineri, E. D. (2015). Professors' and students' conflicting beliefs about translanguaging in the EFL classroom: Dismantling the monolingual bias. *Revista de Linguas Modernas*, 23, 301-328. <https://doi.org/10.15517/rfm.v0i23.22355>
- Estyn. (2002). Developing dual literacy: An Estyn discussion paper. *Journal on Multicultural Studies*, 4(2), 1-28.
- Frith, H., & Gleeson, K. (2004). Clothing and embodiment: Men managing body image and appearance. *Psychology of Men and Masculinity*, 5(1), 40-48. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1524-9220.5.1.40>
- Garcia, O. (2009). *Bilingual education in the 21st century: Global perspective*. Wiley Blackwell.
- Garcia, O., & Li, W. (2014). *Translanguaging: Language, bilingualism and education*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Hamachek, D. (1995). Self-concept and school achievement: Interaction dynamics and a tool for asserting the self-concept component. *Journal of Counselling and Development*, 73(4), 419-425.
- Hannafin, M. J., Hill, J. R., Land, S. M., & Lee, E. (2014). Student-centered, open learning environments: Research, theory, and practice. In M. Spector, M. D. Merrill, J. van Merriënboer & M. P. Driscoll (Eds.), *Handbook of research on educational communications and technology* (pp. 641-651). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-3185-5_51
- Hannaford, E. D., & Alexander, M. (2024). Linguistic diversity in institutional collections: Beyond preservation to valorisation. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2). [in press]

- Hayes, N. (2000). *Doing psychological research Buckingham England*: Open University Press.
- Huang, Y.-W. (2024). Language loss and translingual identities near the Navajo land. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2). [in press]
- Hurst, E., & Mona, M. (2017). Translanguaging as a socially just pedagogy. *Education as Change*, 21(2), 126-148. <https://doi.org/10.17159/1947-9417/2017/2015>
- İlhan, B., & Özkan, Y. (2021). Translanguaging beliefs of dynamic bilinguals in an EFL context. *International Seminar on Language, Education and Culture Proceedings* (pp. 14-18). Universitas Negeri Malang.
- Jalongo, M. R., & Saracho, O. N. (2016). *Writing for publication: Transitions and tools that support scholars' success*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-31650-5>
- Jameel, B., Shaheen, S., & Majid, U. (2018). Introduction to qualitative research for novice investigators. *Undergraduate Research in Natural and Clinical Science and Technology (URNCST) Journal*, 2(6) 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.26685/urncst.57>
- Jørgensen, J. N. (2008). Polylingual languaging around and among children and adolescents. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 5(3), 161-176.
- Jørgensen, J. N., Karrebaek, M. S., Madsen, L. M., & Moller, J. S. (2011). Polylinguaging in super diversity. *Diversities*, 13(2), 23-38.
- Kivunja, C., & Kuyini, A. B. (2017). Understanding and applying research paradigms in educational contexts. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 6(5), 26-41. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v6n5p26>
- Klaus, D. (2003). The use of indigenous languages in early basic education in Papua New Guinea: A model for elsewhere? *Language and Education*, 17(2), 105-111.
- Krause, L. S., & Prinsloo, M. (2016). Translanguaging in a township primary school: Policy and practice. *Southern African Linguistics and Applied Language Studies*, 34(4), 347-357. <https://doi.org/10.2989/16073614.2016.1261039>

- Krueger, R. A., & Casey, M. A. (2000). *Focus groups: A practical guide for applied research*. Sage Publications Inc.
- Kruger-Marais, E. (2024). Subtitling for language acquisition: Eye tracking as predictor of attention allocation in education. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2). [in press]
- Leedy, P. D., and Ormrod, J. E. (2016). *Practical research: Planning and design* (11th ed.). Pearson Education.
- MacSwan, J. (2017). A Multilingual Perspective on Translanguaging. *American Educational Research Journal*, 54(1), 167-201. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831216683935>
- Makalela, L. (2015). Moving out of linguistic boxes: The effects of translanguaging strategies for multilingual classrooms. *Language and Education*, 29(3), 200-217. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500782.2014.994524>
- Makalela, L. (2020). Uncovering the universals of Ubuntu translanguaging in the classroom discourses. *Classroom Discourse*, 10(3-4), 237-251. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19463014.2019.1631198>
- Mapuya, M. (2024). Exploring the contribution of decolonisation epistemologies: Promoting social justice in accounting education. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 131-155.
- Merriam, S. B. (1998). *Qualitative research and case study application in education*. Jossey-Bass.
- Mgijima, V. D., & Makalela, L. (2016). The effects of translanguaging on the bi-literate inferencing strategies of fourth grade learners. *Perspectives in Education*, 34(3), 86-93. <https://doi.org/10.18820/2519593X/pie.v34i3.7>
- Mohajan, H. K. (2018). Qualitative research methodology in social sciences and related subjects. *Journal of Economic Development, Environment and People*, 7, 23-48. <https://doi.org/10.26458/jedep.v7i1.571>
- Motaung, L. B. (2024). Translanguaging pedagogical practice in a tutorial programme at a South African university. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 81-104.

- Ndlangamandla, S. C. (2024). The coloniality of English proficiency and EMI: Decolonization, language equity, and epistemic (in)justice. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 105-130.
- Ndlangamandla, S. C., Chaka C., Shange, T., & Shandu-Phetla, T. (2024). COVID-19 crosslinguistic and multimodal public health communication strategies: social justice or emergency political strategy? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2). [in press]
- Nyimbili, F., & Mwanza, D. S. (2021). Translanguaging challenges faced by teachers and learners in first grade multilingual literacy classrooms in Zambia. *International Journal on Studies in English Language and Literature*, 9(3), 20-31. <https://doi.org/10.20431/2347-3134.0903003>
- Nyumba, T. O., Wilson, K., Derrick, C. J., & Mukherjee, N. (2018). The use of focus group discussion methodology: Insights from two decades of application in conservation. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 9(1), 20-32. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12860>
- Obi, U. K., Ticha, I. K., & Nakhooda, M. (2021). Teaching academic literacy in English for multiple objectives at a university of technology. *The Journal of English as an International Language*, 16(1), 60-76.
- Otherguy, R., García, O., & Reid, W. (2015). Clarifying translanguaging and deconstructing named languages: A perspective from linguistics. *Applied Linguistics Review*, 6(3), 281-307. <https://doi.org/10.1515/applirev-2015-0014>
- Otsuji, E., & Pennycook, A. (2011). Social inclusion and metro lingual practices. *International journal of bilingual education and bilingualism*, 14(4), 413-426. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2011.573065>
- Park, M. S. (2013). Code-switching and translanguaging: Potential functions in multilingual classrooms. *Teachers College, Colombia University Working Papers in TESOL & Applied Linguistics*, 13(2), 50-52. <https://doi.org/10.7916/salt.v13i2.1332>
- Prilutskaya, M. (2021). Examining pedagogical translanguaging: A systematic review of the literature. *Language*, 6(4), 180. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/languages8020144>

- Riswanto, R. (2022). Exploring translanguaging as a pedagogical strategy used by the English teacher in EFL classroom setting. *Jurnal Penelitian Guru Indonesia*, 7(1), 96-103. <https://doi.org/10.29210/021948jpgi0005>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2016). Working on the 'write' path: Improving EFL students' argumentative-writing performance through L1-mediated structural cognitive modification. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 10(4), 131-152. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7514806>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021a). Test affordances or test function? Did we get Messick's message right? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 15(3), 127-140. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7514614>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021b). Washback or backwash? Revisiting the status quo of washback and test impact in EFL contexts. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 8(3), 869-884. <https://doi.org/10.24815/siele.v8i3.21406>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2022). Breaking out of the Gricean vicious cycle: Let's divorce semantics and just agree that there is no meaning in language. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(3), 33-60. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7514602>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2023). EFL classroom, petri dish, panopticon, and free world: How do they merge through action research? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 17(1), 97-116. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7513356>
- Sefotho, M. P. (2022). Ubuntu translanguaging as a systematic approach to language teaching in multilingual classrooms in South Africa. *Journal for Language Teaching*, 56(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.56285/jltVol56iss1a5416>
- Shannon, F. (2011). Interactionist and input theories of second language acquisition and their pedagogical implications. *The English Language Literature Society*, 61, 17-28.
- Stoop, C. (2017). Children's rights to mother-tongue education in a multilingual world: A comparative analysis between South Africa and Germany. *PER/PELJ*, 20, 1-35. <https://doi.org/10.17159/1727-3781/2017/v20n0a820>

- Szelei, N., Sofia, A. P., & Tinoca, L. A. F. (2021). Teaching in multilingual classrooms: Strategies from a case study in Portugal. *Revista Brasileira d'Educação*, 26, 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s1413-24782021260038>
- Tabatabaei, R. (2019). *Translanguaging in ESL classrooms in Sweden: From the students' point of view* [Unpublished master's thesis]. Stockholms Universitet.
- Taqi, H. A., & Shuqair, K. M. (2014). Evaluating the students' language proficiency in the English Department, college of basic education in Kuwait. *British Journal of Education*, 2(6), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.37745/bje.2013>
- Thomas, W. P., & Collier, V. (1997). *School effectiveness for language minority students*. National Clearinghouse for Bilingual Education.
- Tumansery, G. S., & Munden, J. (2020). Communicative competence in English upper secondary school curricula in Indonesia. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 14(3), 1-26.
- Turuk, M. C. (2008). The relevance and implications of Vygotsky's sociocultural theory in the second language classroom. *ARECLS*, 5, 244-262.
- Williams, M. (1994). Motivation in foreign and second language learning: An interactive perspective. *Educational and Child Psychology*, 11, 77-84.
- Włosowicz, T. M. (2020). The use of elements of translanguaging in the teaching third or additional languages: Some advantages and limitations. *Multidisciplinary Journal of School of Education*, 9(17), 136-169. <http://doi.org/0000-0001-8767-9332>
- Xu, Y., & Fang, F. (2024). Promoting educational equity: The implementation of translanguaging pedagogy in English language education. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 53-80.
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case study research and applications: Design and methods* (6th ed.). Sage.
- Yuzlu, M. Y., & Dikilitas, K. (2022). Translanguaging in the development of EFL learners' foreign language skills in Turkish context. *Innovation in Language Learning and Teaching* 16(2), 176-190. <http://doi.org/10.1080/17501229.2021.1892698>

Zhou, L., Li, F., Wu, S., & Zhou, M. (2020). School's out but class's on, the largest online education in the world today: Taking China's practical exploration during the COVID-19 epidemic prevention and control as an example. *Best Evidence of Chinese Education*, 4(2), 501-519. <https://doi.org/10.15354/bece.20.ar023>